

SYNCHRONOUS INTERPRETATION AND ITS PECULIARITIES

Abdullayev Azizkhon Rustamovich

teacher of the English Department,
faculty of international relations,
University of world economy
and the diplomacy.

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Synchronous interpretation, also known as simultaneous interpretation, is a type of interpretation in which the interpreter translates the speaker's words in real-time. This means that the interpreter speaks at the same time as the speaker, using specialized equipment such as headphones and microphones to hear and transmit the interpretation.

Synchronous interpretation requires a high level of skill and concentration from the interpreter, as they must listen to the speaker while simultaneously translating their words into the target language. This can be mentally taxing and requires a great deal of focus and stamina. One of the key peculiarities of synchronous interpretation is the need for specialized equipment, such as soundproof booths, microphones, and headsets. This equipment is necessary to ensure that the interpreter can hear the speaker clearly and that their interpretation is transmitted accurately to the audience.

Simultaneous translation is new to translation despite its appearance, considerable scientific research has been done. Simultaneous translation and its strategies are in linguistics R. Setton, M. Lederer, B. Moser, D. Seleskovitch, D. Snelling, D. Gile, G. V. Chernov, A. F. Shiryayev, A. L. Chernyaxovskaya, V. M. Ilyuxin 4, studied by Uzbek linguists in the study of linguists like H.Khamidov. In this article, synchronous translation strategies are implemented in the English-Uzbek language combination one of the early studies.

Another peculiarity of synchronous interpretation is the need for a team of interpreters. Due to the mental strain involved in simultaneous interpretation, interpreters typically work in teams of two or more, taking turns interpreting in shifts of 20-30 minutes.

Synchronous interpretation is commonly used in settings such as international conferences, business meetings, and political summits. It allows participants from different linguistic backgrounds to communicate effectively and ensures that important information is not lost in translation.

Synchronous interpretation, also known as simultaneous interpretation, is a highly complex and demanding form of language mediation. This practice

involves rendering spoken language from one language to another in real time, typically used in conferences, international events, and high-level diplomatic gatherings. Let's delve into the theoretical underpinnings and key peculiarities of synchronous interpretation:

Synchronous interpretation is grounded in psycholinguistic principles, highlighting the intricate cognitive processes that underpin the interpreter's ability to comprehend, analyze, and produce language in real time.

- Perception and Production: Interpreters engage in rapid auditory processing, comprehension, and instant production of language, requiring acute perceptual and cognitive abilities.

- Memory and Recall: Synchronous interpretation relies on working memory capacity, involving the retention of information in short-term memory while processing and producing language output.

- Decoding and Re-encoding: Interpreters analyze source-language input and convert it into the target language, skillfully navigating complex linguistic structures, idiomatic expressions, and cultural references.

- Conveying Intonation and Emotion: Synchronous interpreters must convey not only the content of the speaker's message but also the speaker's intonation, emotion, and style, adding an additional layer of complexity to the interpretation process.

- Continuous Information Flow: The non-stop nature of synchronous interpretation demands intense concentration and the ability to seamlessly process and relay information without a break.

- Immediate Language Selection: Interpreters must make split-second decisions about grammatical structures, lexical choices, and cultural equivalents in real time, requiring rapid problem-solving skills.

- Adaptation to Rapid Speech: Synchronous interpreters operate in high-pressure environments, adapting to speakers with rapid speech patterns and varying delivery styles.

- Ethical Constraints: Interpreters must maintain strict confidentiality, impartiality, and neutrality, adhering to professional codes of conduct and ethical guidelines.

- Cultural Sensitivity: Ensuring cultural sensitivity in interpreting, managing potential challenges related to cultural nuances, sensitivity, and potential biases in language choice.

- **Technical Proficiency:** Interpreters must be proficient in using specialized interpretation equipment, including microphones, headsets, and booth setups, to facilitate seamless communication.

- **Environmental Adaptation:** Synchronous interpretation often takes place in soundproof booths to enhance focus and reduce external distractions, necessitating an ability to adapt to the physical environment.

- **Continuous Skill Development:** Synchronous interpreters engage in rigorous training programs that focus on language proficiency, cognitive skills, and domain-specific knowledge related to the subject matter of events and conferences.

- **Continuing Education:** Continuous professional development and ongoing language enhancement are crucial for interpreters to stay abreast of linguistic developments, terminology, and cultural changes in diverse fields.

Synchronous interpretation presents a remarkable blend of linguistic, cognitive, and pragmatic intricacies, demanding a high degree of linguistic proficiency, cognitive agility, and cultural understanding. Navigating this challenging form of language mediation requires a unique set of skills, including acute cognitive processing, linguistic dexterity, and rapid decision-making abilities.

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